

Stability Constants of Complexes of 7-Dicyclohexylaminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline with Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II) and Manganese(II)

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The stability constants of 7-dicyclohexylaminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} were determined potentiometrically in 3:1 (v/v) dioxane-water mixture at ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$. The successive formation constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined employing Irving-Rossotti method. The order of stability constants is $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$, which is in accordance with Irving-Williams rule.

POTENTIOMETRIC studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} with 7-dicyclohexylaminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline. The dissociation constants of the ligand and formation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by modified Bjerrum's method at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 3:1 (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1μ by the addition of NaClO_4 .

Experimental

The ligand 7-dicyclohexylaminomethyl-8-hydroxyquinoline was prepared by adding formaldehyde to dicyclohexylamine (0.02 mol each) with constant shaking. The mixture was allowed to cool for 15 min and then added 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.02 mol) in 20 ml ethanol. After adding a drop of conc. HCl, the mixture was refluxed for 45 min at $70-80^\circ$ with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for a day. The solid obtained was then separated and crystallized in solvent ether and dried to yield yellowish brown product, m.p. $135-140^\circ$. The purity of the ligand was further confirmed by tlc.

The dioxane used was purified by the standard method¹. Double distilled water was used throughout the experiment. The ligand solution was prepared in purified dioxane. Metal solutions were prepared in perchloric acid and the solutions of HClO_4 and NaClO_4 in double distilled water.

pH values were recorded employing Philips PP 9045 digital pH meter. For pH measurements following sets of solutions were prepared and titrated against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution (0.5 M) in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

- 5 ml (0.1 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml (0.70 M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml dioxane.
- 5 ml (0.1 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml (0.70 M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml (0.05 M) ligand + 25 ml dioxane.
- 2.5 ml (0.1 M) HClO_4 + 2.5 ml (0.01 M) metal solution in (0.1 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml (0.70 M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml (0.05 M) ligand + 25 ml dioxane.

The total volume of each system was kept at 40 ml maintaining 3:1 (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The appropriate correction factor for converting pH meter readings (B values) to $-\log[\text{H}^+]$ in 3:1 (v/v) dioxane-water was applied² and the curves were plotted accordingly.

The ligand did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions as indicated by the rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titrations and by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after 2 h.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves of solutions (a) and (b) $\bar{n}A$ values at various B values were calculated and plotted against B using the formula of Irving and Rossotti³. The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H were evaluated from half-integral points at $\bar{n}A = 0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. The values so obtained were further corroborated by the straight line plots of $\log [\bar{n}A/1 - \bar{n}A]$ vs B, and $\log [(2 - \bar{n}A)/\bar{n}A - 1]$ vs B, respectively.

From the titration curves of solutions (b) and (c), \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. Metal ligand formation curves (Fig. 1) obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL were utilized to calculate successive stability constants of metal complexes using Rossotti's computational techniques³. The formation curves for Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} are complete at

Fig. 1. Metal ligand formation curves.

both the ends, hence values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were obtained by (i) interpolating at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 , respectively (half integration method), (ii) least square method, (iii) mid point method. The formation curves for Co^{II} and Mn^{II} are however incomplete in upper half portion due to the occurrence of precipitates and hence $\log K_1$ is calculated by half integration and mid point methods, and $\log K_2$ by mid point method using the equation

$$\log K_1 \cdot K_2 = 2pL \quad (\text{at } \bar{n} = 1.0).$$

The calculated values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ along with the protonation constants of the ligand have been reported in Table 1. The results indicate that

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF 7-DICYCLOHEXYLAMINOMETHYL-8-HYDROXYQUINOLINE
Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1$

	H^+	Cu^{II}	Ni^{II}	Co^{II}	Mn^{II}
$\log K_1$	11.45	a 11.70 b 11.596 c 11.70	10.65 10.62 10.65	10.42	10.0
$\log K_2$	4.3	a 9.75 b 9.963 c 10.32	8.9 9.490 9.05	— — 7.78	— — 6.14

a = Half integration method, b = Least square method, c = Mid point method.

the stability of the different complexes investigated follow the order $\text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Co}^{II} > \text{Mn}^{II}$, which is in accordance with Irving-Williams rule⁴.

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